

Reproducibility assessment: “Plotly.plus, an Improved Dataset for Visualization Recommendation”

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This report aims to assess the reproducibility of the results in the 2022 paper “Plotly.plus, an Improved Dataset for Visualization Recommendation” by reconstructing the models used in the paper and trying to train the models on the datasets provided. Ultimately, we were unable to reproduce the results exactly, our results however suggest a similar conclusion than that of the original paper.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: visualization recommendation, deep learning

1 INTRODUCTION

The 2022 paper “Plotly.plus, an Improved Dataset for Visualization Recommendation” [3] aims to improve on the “Plotly” data set used in training models for visualization recommendation. The result is an augmented data set called “Plotly.plus”

The paper concludes with an evaluation section presenting the performance of two machine learning models in classifying whether images from the “Plotly” or “Plotly.plus” datasets were in the “insightful” or “not insightful” class. The findings are summarized in Figure 1. In this report, we are trying to reproduce these results.

2 OVERVIEW

The “Plotly” data set consists of combinations of data sets, visualization types and variable mappings which were sourced from the public feed of Plotly visualizations made by users. These combinations are thought of being “insightful” (hereafter denoted by \mathcal{V}^+) and are used as desirable examples in the training of recommendation systems. Conversely, all other combinations are implicitly deemed “not insightful” (denoted by \mathcal{V}^-) and therefore not desirable.

The authors note that after generating \mathcal{V}^- explicitly, the visualizations resulting from the contained combinations were often visually similar to those in \mathcal{V}^+ . Furthermore, they argue that the criterion of being a combination chosen by a user of the software does not guarantee it being particularly insightful. In order to construct an improved data set, the authors selected scatter and line charts from the original data set (the most frequent types), generated \mathcal{V}^- and then aimed to reclassify the combined set by using an image clustering algorithms on visualization images generated from the combinations in \mathcal{V}^+ as well as \mathcal{V}^- and manually labelling the resulting clusters as “insightful” and “not insightful”.

3 REPRODUCTION

3.1 Reconstructing “Model 81”

In [1], a detailed summary of the layer configuration is given. The convolutional and pooling layers are specified to use 3x3 windows. Combined with the documented output size it can be determined that the convolutional layers also use padding since the input and output sizes are the same.

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Fig. 1. The reported classification performance with “Old corpus” referring to the “Plotly” dataset and “New corpus” referring to “Plotly.plus”. Reprinted from [3]

Unspecified parameters are omitted, using the defaults provided by the TensorFlow and Keras libraries if possible. As a further reference to inform such choices, the implementations of VGG16¹ and VGG19² (the models inspiring the simplified version in the mentioned paper) in the Keras library were used.

Using these resources, we set a dropout rate of 0.5 in the dropout layers. We furthermore employed the adaptation mentioned in [3] of reducing the dimensionality of the final output to work with two classes instead of ten: our final layer has an output dimension of one and uses a sigmoid activation function (a common practice in a binary classification problem).

3.2 Reconstructing “Model 97”

The model described in [2] is comprised of a combination of an image preprocessing pipeline using Canny edge detection and a convolutional neural net whose architecture is specified in the paper.

The image preprocessing pipeline is described as converting the images to greyscale, resizing them to 120x120 pixels and using the Canny edge detection algorithm as implemented in the library OpenCV³. Image examples in the paper are shown as having black edges on white background, so the images resulting from Canny edge detection (white on black) are inverted. For a visual comparison of an image pictured in [2] and resulting from our preprocessing, see Figures 2 and 3. These preprocessing steps are performed by us beforehand and the preprocessed images are stored on disk.

Most parameters are given or deducible in the case of the described CNN. The final layer was (as with “Model 81”) changed to a dense layer with an output dimension of 1 and a sigmoid activation function.

An aspect that does not seem possible to replicate for us is that according to [2] images were resized without changing their aspect ratio. We are provided with rectangular images in the dataset and therefore would either have to crop them or change their aspect ratio. We decided on doing the latter to not lose potentially crucial information from some of the images.

3.3 Model training and evaluation

For both models, no details are given on how the training was performed. In [3, p. 4387], the information is given that a “10-fold cross evaluation on the original and improved Plotly dataset, with 80% training and 20% test” was performed.

¹available at: https://github.com/keras-team/keras-applications/blob/master/keras_applications/vgg16.py

²available at: https://github.com/keras-team/keras-applications/blob/master/keras_applications/vgg19.py

³see an example at: https://docs.opencv.org/4.x/da/d22/tutorial_py_canny.html

Fig. 2. Sample image after preprocessing as pictured in [2, p. 7]

Fig. 3. Sample image from the Plotly.plus dataset after performing the reproduced preprocessing described above

Since the combination of an 80%/20%-split and using 10-fold cross-validation does not seem compatible to us we employed an evaluation strategy of splitting the dataset into 80% and 20% parts, evaluating on the 20% not used for training. We then repeated this process five times with different random seeds.

The model is compiled with the “Adam” optimizer, uses “binary_crossentropy” loss and returns six evaluation metrics: true positives (TP), false negatives (FN), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN), precision and recall. The reported F1 value is computed as the harmonic average of precision and recall. The models are trained for five epochs using the fit method. Finally, the model’s performance is evaluated on the test data not used in training the model via the “evaluate” method implemented in the “Model” class, returning the metrics above.

Referencing the following passage, we also considered training the models on only examples of the “1” class from the “Plotly” dataset. However, since the passage is not completely clear how the training was performed exactly, we concluded that training the models also on the provided complement set \mathcal{V}^- of the “Plotly” dataset would prove more instructive as to how clearly \mathcal{V}^- and \mathcal{V}^+ could be discerned in the respective datasets.

The histograms show that performance is more than doubled for both systems when trained with the new Plotly.plus corpus. We can reasonably assume that this increase in accuracy is achieved both because systems are learning from positive and negative examples, **rather than just from positive**, and because there is less noise in the dataset. [3, p. 4387, emphasis added]

3.4 Data loading

The data is provided by the authors split into line charts and scatterplots. We combine these images preserving the class assignment into “0” or “not insightful” and “1” or “insightful” which the models are supposed to learn. The datasets are loaded with the function “image_dataset_from_directory” implemented in the Keras library. In this function, a validation split of 20% is specified. This is repeated five times with different seeds for each model, so each model is repeatedly trained with different data splits.

4 RESULTS

We were not able to precisely reproduce the results in the paper, since the information on the training of the models and the exact mode of computing the results is mostly missing.

Finally, it proved computationally infeasible to try many more parameter permutations and a larger amount of training epochs while also repeating the training a number of times. If the models were trained for considerably longer, this could alter the results. We however doubt that they were in the cited paper since precision and recall values in our results exceed those in [3] with both datasets.

The results on both datasets are largely comparable across the two models, they are however much higher in both precision and recall than in the cited paper. The results of the models are still markedly improved on all metrics for the “Plotly.plus” dataset.

Fig. 4. Performance metrics of the models on both datasets

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